

Quantum Time-Independent Particle and the Loss of Direction Knowledge?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 22, 2025

In (1), it is argued that there is an inconsistency due to the fact that a time-independent bound state wavefunction $W(x)$ has zeros. In particular, (1) argues that if a particle is at the left hand side or right hand side of the system, it must pass to the other side and so the probability $W(x)W(x)$ cannot be 0 at any point, otherwise the particle cannot get from one side to another.

Here, we argue that the use of probability to solve a problem implies an inherent uncertainty of some kind. It might be suggested that this inherent uncertainty is simply due to a lack of information and that using probability is a quick way to solve the problem without worrying about excessive details. We suggest, however, that even in Newtonian mechanics, it seems that there is a probabilistic feature present in two body collisions which conserve momentum (and energy if they are elastic). Given two colliding particles in an elastic collision with energies e_1 and e_2 , what is the outcome? Based on energy, one might argue that any e_i, e_j pair such that $e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j$ is suitable and that there is no reason to think that any pair carries more weight than the other. In other words, trying to determine which e_i, e_j pair is created in a collision seems like asking for too much information and accepting the above statistical assumption is fine, even at the Newtonian particle level.

We have argued that applying these ideas to free particles leads to $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$ (one dimension) as a complex probability as there is no energy distribution as in an ideal gas. Each free particle has the same modulus of probability such that any e_i, e_j pair or p_{xi}, p_{xj} pair (one dimension) has the same probability if they have the same sum. This, however, leads to a stochastic situation in x and t which one might not have expected. In other words, there is an inherent uncertainty present associated with more than e_i, e_j or p_{xi}, p_{xj} (one dimension) pairs having the same weight. Given that $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$ is a probability, one might consider time independent problems and try to solve them probabilistically. This involves introducing uncertainty into the problem which may actually be linked to the solution. In particular. If one considers a two slit system, a particle passes through one slit or the other, but one does not know which and writes and OR (sum) of $\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2)$ where r_1 is a vector from slit 1 to a point on the screen and r_2 , from slit 2 to the same point. The result (which involves superposition) requires that one give up the notion of knowing through which slit the particle passes.

Similarly, solving for a bound state (time independent) means giving up knowing in which direction a particle moves, as we discuss. Thus, we argue that one cannot say that a particle moves from one side of the system to the other as in (1) and so must pass through a 0 point of the wavefunction $W(x)$. The wavefunction $W(x)$ which has the zero is created by giving up information on the direction of motion, just like one gives up information on knowing through which slit a particle passes. Thus, we argue that there is no inconsistency based on the ideas of probability of $W(x)$ having 0 points.

Free Particle Probability

Why should a free particle have a probability in the first place? It may be described by $x=vt$ (along the ray of motion) and this is deterministic in Newtonian mechanics. There is, however, a statistical feature present in Newtonian mechanics, but it involves two body collisions and conservation. Momentum is always conserved and in an elastic collision, energy is conserved. If one considers a particle with energy e_1 colliding elastically with one with e_2 , then from an energy point of view, the outcome may be any e_i, e_j pairs such that:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j \quad ((1))$$

It seems reasonable to argue that all e_i, e_j pairs satisfying ((1)) carry the same weight, because even in Newtonian mechanics one does not know details to the level of predicting e_i, e_j . In other words, there is an inherent probability, but only at the collision level. We suggest that this means that there must be a free particle probability, but it cannot be real because one free particle does not have a different weight from another, unlike $p(e)$ for a particle in an ideal gas. There is no equilibrium distribution of energy for free particles. Thus, one would expect a power law, $\exp(iC_e)$ and $\exp(iC_2p)$ one dimension so each free particle has the same modulus of probability. As argued in previous notes, p is a vector and so p and $-p$ (one dimension) cannot have different probability values. This requires introducing a co-ordinate system factor which removes the x -axis direction, i.e

$$\exp(i p \Delta x) \quad ((2))$$

To make the probability invariant to changes in frames, one may generalize to:

$$\exp(-iEt + ipx) \text{ one dimension} \quad ((3))$$

If one has collisions, it seems that one should use ((3)) to describe a free particle. The curious feature is that there is now not only uncertainty in e_i, e_j and p_x, p_y pairs, but also in x and t for a single particle. There is a second uncertainty.

The Time-Independent Bound State Situation

This leads to a bound state case which we assume is time-independent. Such a bound state may be considered to have a center-of-mass and act as an overall particle itself. This means that it can collide and so should be represented by $\exp(-iEt + iP_x)$ where P is total momentum. A bound state, however, is usually thought of as not moving, so $P_{\text{total}} = 0$. If this is the case, then one should use $\exp(ip_x)$ (time-independent scenario) and $\exp(-ip_x)$ to describe interactions with a potential. In other words, one uses the probabilistic feature of ((3)), but also gives up the notion of following the particle's direction of motion, just as the 2-slit problem gives up the feature of knowing through which slit the particle passes. In previous notes, we have argued that due to the uncertainty in x due to the wavelength, one cannot really follow the particle's

direction, but here we suggest that a priori, one sets up a probabilistic scenario in which there is no information about particle direction because overall momentum must be 0.

One may show in fact that:

$$\int W (-i\hbar/dx W) dx = 0 \quad ((4))$$

because if W is even, then dW/dx is odd and the product of an even and odd function is odd. The same conclusion holds for W odd.

Thus, the use of the wavefunction $W(x)$ comes with a significant statistical price to pay. One must give up the notion of knowing the direction in which a particle moves. The problem, however, is still solved in a completely consistent statistical manner.

One might ask: Why is $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ used in the first place? Newtonian mechanics suggests that a particle is acted upon by $V(x)$ (potential) dx . Here dx is tiny and $\hbar/p =$ wavelength is larger than dx for low energy levels and so the Newtonian picture must be dropped. One must, however, still have an interaction with the potential involving momentum and the inherent uncertainty:

$$V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx) \rightarrow \exp(ik_1x) \exp(ip_1x) = \exp(ik_2x) \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((5))$$

still remains. Thus, using $\exp(ipx)$ seems to be consistent with this statistical viewpoint.

The goal is now to find E (total energy) and $W(x)$. This is done using the Schrodinger equation in a time-independent scenario:

$$E W(x) = -\hbar^2/2m d^2/dx^2 W(x) + V(x) W(x) \text{ with boundary conditions} \quad ((6))$$

$$W(x) \text{ may be written as a linear superposition: } \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Spatial density} = W(x)W(x) \quad ((8))$$

$W(x)$ has 0 points, but we have already argued that there is no notion in which direction the particle moves. Thus, from a probabilistic calculation point of view, we argue that one cannot make the claim of (1) that a particle on the left hand side must move to the right and in doing so pass through a 0 of $W(x)$, a point at which it does not exist. If one retained the notion of direction motion, then the argument of (1) would hold, but the Schrodinger equation involves a statistical calculation which relinquishes the direction motion of the particle and so it cannot be brought back later in an argument such as that of (1). We argue that there is no inconsistency.

Measuring Momentum

The wavefunction $W(x)$ has zeros which describe a resolution in space we argue. It is possible to knock a particle out of bound state and in doing so determine its momentum. In fact, doing this multiple times, should yield the momentum probability:

$$P(p) = a(p)a(p) \text{ where } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((9))$$

If one knows p , however, one does not know x and so a particle with p may have come from any x point, including $W(x)=0$ points. By measuring p , the bound system (superposition) is now broken. This is equivalent to measuring the slit through which a particle passes, a measurement process which destroys 2-slit interference. Thus, in quantum mechanics, a probabilistic calculation may involve giving up information, such as momentum direction or a slit through which a particle passes. Forcing such a measurement may actually break the quantum system represented by a probability calculation involving $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ or $\exp(ip \cdot r1) + \exp(ip \cdot r2)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, probability involves relinquishing some sort of information. In probabilistic calculations, one needs to know a priori which information is being relinquished because one cannot then go back after the calculation is performed and consider the result in the context of knowing the relinquished information. In the case of a 2-slit experiment, one does not know through which slit the particle passed. One can solve this problem probabilistically using $\exp(ip \cdot r1) + \exp(ip \cdot r2)$, but this explicitly assumes that one does not know the slit through which the particle passed. One cannot consider classical arguments which pretend that one knows through which slit the particle passed after the probabilistic calculation is performed.

Likewise, we argue that a time-dependent bound state calculator involves relinquishing information about the direction of motion, i.e. using $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ in the wavefunction $W(x)$. This is necessary because one assumes a total momentum of zero for the bound system. This means explicitly that such a probabilistic calculation cannot then be interpreted in terms of direction of particle motion. We suggest that this is what occurs in the argument of (1). The authors note that $W(x)$ has 0 points meaning that $W(x)W(x)=0$ excludes a particle from such points. They then argue that if a particle moves from left to right (or vice versa), it must pass through a 0 point which is impossible, leading to an inconsistency. We argue that the statistical calculation of $W(x)$ relinquishes information about directional motion and so one cannot make arguments about a particle moving from left to right or vice versa. Thus, we argue that there is no inconsistency with $W(x)$ having 0 points. These define a kind of resolution in space, it seems.

References

1. Purwanto, A. et al. Inconsistency of Probability Density in Quantum Mechanics and Its Solution (May 2012)
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